

ARAŞTIRMA MAKALESİ

RESEARCH ARTICLE

DOES THE CRP/ALBUMIN RATIO SERVE AS A MARKER IN THE EVALUATION OF CLINICAL COURSE IN PATI- ENTS COMING TO THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT WITH ISCHEMIC CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASE?

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ABSTRACT

Our aim in this study is to seek an answer to the question of whether the CRP/Albumin ratio can be a reliable indicator of the clinical course in patients presenting to emergency departments with ischemic cerebrovascular disease. Method: This is a retrospective study and included patients over the age of 18 who came to the emergency department with ischemic cerebrovascular disease between 01 June 2021 and 01 December 2021. The study was conducted on routine blood samples taken from patients. At the end of the analysis, the average age of the patients was 72.8±12.9 (min: 25-max: 97). 54% (n=32) of the patients had comorbidities. CRP and CRP/ALB ratios of the patients were found to be significantly higher in the mortal group than in the healthy group (<.05). As a result, we think that early CRP levels and CRP/Albumin ratio may help predict the in-hospital mortality of these patients.

Key Words: Ischemic cerebrovascular disease, CRP/Albumin ratio, C-reactive protein (CRP)

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INTRODUCTION

Acute ischemic cerebrovascular disease (CVD) essentially refers to brain tissue necrosis caused by hypoxia and ischemia due to tissue perfusion disorder (1). CVD patients often have varying degrees of neurological findings, and permanent damage or death may occur (2). It is important to investigate serum biomarkers related to the diagnosis and prediction of CVD. C-reactive protein (CRP), the subject of our study, is an acute phase reactant triggered by interleukin-6 (IL-6) secreted in response to the first phase of the infectious or inflammatory process. serves as. CRP has both anti-inflammatory and pro-inflammatory properties. Persistent elevation of CRP is a marker of chronic inflammation and its elevation is seen in autoimmune diseases. Clinicians more often associate a high CRP value with a 90% bacterial infection (3,4). In critically ill patients, high CRP levels are considered as a poor prognosis (5).

Albumin is the most abundant protein in plasma. Some of the situations in which albumin increases are shock, dehydration, hemoconcentration, and excessive intravenous administration of concentrated albumin. Albumin is a negative acute phase reactant and appears to decrease in more severe and critically ill patients. Some of these are sepsis, postoperative or trauma, malnutrition, renal failure, burns, liver cirrhosis, chronic infections, protein-losing enteropathies and malignant diseases (6). Some animal studies have shown that it has significant neuroprotective effects in ischemic stroke models; These effects mainly manifest themselves as reducing the brain infarct volume and improving the neurological score(7).

In this study, we investigated the usability of the CRP/Albumin ratio in evaluating the clinical course of patients admitted to the emergency department due to cerebrovascular disease in the critical patient category.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Patients aged 18 and over who applied to Karaman Training and Research Hospital Emergency Medicine Clinic between 01. 06. 2021- 01.12.2021 with suspicion of acute ischemic stroke and diagnosed with acute ischemic stroke by radiological examination were included in our study. Patients were classified as group 1, and those in the healthy group screening were classified as group 2. It was planned to record laboratory information such as age, gender, routine blood tests such as CRP and Albumin of all patients included in the study. The first CRP, white blood cell count (WBC), neutrophil and lymphocyte quantitative counts and percentages taken for evaluation as soon as they are accepted at the time of application (the highest value or first value seen during follow-up for each parameter) will be recorded as laboratory findings. All these data will be scanned retrospectively from the hospital system.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Inc., version 20.0; Chicago, IL) will be used in statistical analyses. All statistical data were made with SPSS 20.0 version program for Windows.

Kolmogorov Smirnov test and skewness-kurtosis method were used to evaluate the normal distribution of all variables. In addition, the normal distribution of the data was evaluated with histogram, one of the graphical methods. Descriptive statistics were used in the demographic analysis of the patients. Numerical values in the study data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and minimum-maximum values. It was planned to use the significance test of the difference between two means in independent groups, Mann-Whitney-U test and Kruskal Wallis test to evaluate the data. Statistical significance level was accepted as $p < 0.05$. In the evaluation of 28-day mortality according to the clinical results of the patients, CRP and CRP/Albumin proportional parameters were evaluated with the ROC curve (Receiver-Operating Characteristics Curve).

Data Collection

Age, gender, clinical outcomes, survival and blood parameters of the patients included in the study. All laboratory data, including complete blood count (Mindray BC6800 device), serum biochemistry (Beckman Coulter AU 5800 and Beckman Coulter AU 680 devices), biochemistry, were obtained from patient files and hospital information system. were scanned and recorded retrospectively. Survival data of the patients were recorded in the hospital information system.

RESULTS

The study included 60 patients with CVD who were admitted to the emergency department and hospitalized with the diagnosis of cerebrovascular disease between 01 June and 01 December, and 45 control group patients without CVD disease. In the study, 20.3% ($n = 12$) of the patient group was planned to be treated and discharged home, 37.3% ($n = 22$) was planned to be hospitalized and 42.5% ($n = 26$) was planned to be admitted to intensive care. Demographic data and comorbidity distributions of the patients are given in Table 1. According to this; 34 of the patients were male (56%) and 26 (44%) were female. The average age of the patients was 72.8 ± 12.9 (min: 25-max: 97). 54% ($n=32$) of the patients had comorbidities. Its comorbidities are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of cerebrovascular patients

Demographic Characteristics Independent Variables (IVs)	Name of Characteristics	Number	Percent (%)	Mean	Sdt. Dev.
Gender	Female	26	44		
	Male	34	56		
Age				72.8	12.9
Comorbidity		32	54		
Hypertension		26	42		
CAD		29	47.8		
Discharged home healthy Service tracking Intensive care follow-up		12	20.3		
		23	37.3		
		25	42.4		
Clinical course	Patient who died	15	24.1		
	Living patients	45	75.9		

Laboratory data of CVD patients and differences between groups

The minimum and maximum values in laboratory findings of CVO patients are shown in Table 2. Although the WBC value of the patients in Group 1 was higher than that in Group 2, there was no statistically significant difference ($p > .05$). Neutrophil, lymphocyte, CRP values and CRP/Alb ratios were found to be significantly higher in group 1 than in group 2. This difference was also found to be statistically significant ($p < .05$). However, as seen in the table, the difference in WBC value was not statistically significant in the two groups ($p \geq .05$).

Table 2. Laboratory data of CVD patients and differences between groups

Laboratory parameters	1.Group(Mean±Standard Deviation)	2. Group (Mean±Standard Deviation)	P value
WBC(4.0-10.0 × 10⁹/L)	10.2±3.2	7.5±1.5	0.166
Neutrophils (2.0-6.0× 10⁹/L)	6.9±3.8	4.6±1.2	0.002*
Lymphocyte(1.1-3.2 ×10⁹/L)	1.6±1.3	2.9±4.3	0.001*
Albumin	35.1±5.1	40.8±2.4	<0.05*
C-reactive protein(0-6 mg/L)	35.1±53.1	2.9±1.6	<0.05*
CRP/Albumin	1.3±2.1	0.07±0.04	<0.05*
As statistical analysis, Mann-Whitney U test was used. * =p<0.05 was considered significant.			

When the survival of the patient group was evaluated, 75.9% (n = 45) survived and 24.1% (n = 15) died. The minimum and maximum values of laboratory findings according to the survival of CVO patients are shown in Table 3. When the 28-day survival was evaluated, the difference in WBC, Neutrophil and Lymphocyte values of the mortal patients compared to the surviving patients was not statistically significant (p≥ .05). CRP and CRP/ALB ratios were found to be significantly higher in the mortal group than in the healthy group (<.05) (Table 3).

Table 3. 28-day survival laboratory values between groups

Laboratory parameters	Living patients(Mean±Standard Deviation)	Patient who died (Mean±Standard Deviation)	P value
WBC(4.0-10.0 × 10⁹/L)	9.6±4	8.7±4.6	0.093
Neutrophils (2.0-6.0× 10⁹/L)	7.4±4	5.9±2.6	0.88
Lymphocyte(1.1-3.2 ×10⁹/L)	1.7±1.4	1.2±0.4	0.16
C-reactive protein(0-6 mg/L)	27.3±32.4	82.4±77.6	0.001*
Albumin	35.5±5.1	33.6±6.1	0.11
CRP/Albumin	0.8±1.1	3±3.2	0.002*
As statistical analysis, Mann-Whitney U test was used. * =p<0.05 was considered significant.			

ROC analysis for CRP, CRP/Albumin parameters

In order to evaluate the 28-day survival of CVO patients, ROC curve and AUC, cut-off, sensitivity and specificity were analyzed to distinguish CRP/ALB ratios and CRP laboratory parameters to guide the clinician about the patient's condition during patient follow-up. In addition, the cut-off points, sensitivity and specificity of the mortality values of these laboratory parameters in CVD patients were analyzed with the ROC curve. Parameters with AUC <0.6 and not statistically significant ($P>0.05$) were excluded. For the CRP/ALB ratio, the AUC, cut-off, sensitivity, and specificity were 0.731, 1.03, 78%, and 73.4%, respectively. CRP parameter AUC, cut-off, sensitivity, specificity were 0.736, 29.2, 78.6% and 70%, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1. ROC analysis for CRP, CRP/Albumin parameters

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, we aimed to investigate whether we could use the CRP/Albumin ratio as a biomarker in patients admitted to the emergency department with suspicion of acute ischemic stroke and diagnosed with acute ischemic stroke by radiological examination. Main findings: We saw that CRP and CRP/Albumin ratio were higher in group 1, which we classified as the patient group, and albumin alone was lower than the other group 2. However, within group 1, there were significant differences in Albumin, CRP and CRP/Albumin values between survivors and non-survivors. This can also tell us that the CRP/Albumin ratio may be a useful parameter in predicting mortality.

Recent studies have drawn attention to the role of inflammation in acute brain ischemia (8). CRP is an acute phase reactant synthesized by hepatocytes and regulated by proinflammatory cytokines, especially interleukin (IL)-6. CRP levels can be obtained quickly and easily compared to proinf-

lammatory cytokines, including IL-6, IL-1 β , and nucleotide-binding domain and leucine-rich repeat protein-3 (NLRP3), making CRP testing superior to proinflammatory cytokines. In addition, CRP levels were positively correlated with infarct volume compared with other laboratory tests and proinflammatory cytokines (5).

High CRP levels may cause long-term functional problems in patients with ischemic stroke. Acute local inflammation and inflammatory cytokine levels are altered in patients with ischemic brain injury due to arterial occlusion. CRP levels may reflect the extent of cerebral infarction. The risk of death and cardiovascular mortality is high in ischemic stroke patients with early CRP elevation (9).

Albumin levels may be related to nutritional status and clinical outcomes in critically ill patients. At the same time, as an inflammatory response, albumin levels may decrease due to decreased hepatic synthesis and increased vascular permeability. Similarly, in patients with intracranial hemorrhage, serum albumin may be related to the acute inflammatory response and the severity of intracranial hemorrhage(10). Albumin is the most abundant protein component in cerebrospinal fluid and plasma. C-reactive protein is a sensitive marker of acute inflammation. Infection triggers an inflammatory response such that CRP/albumin increases. In a study conducted by HF Hayati et al. in central nervous system (CNS) infections such as encephalitis, meningitis or myelitis, they stated that there was an increase in the CRP/albumin ratio and that it could be an indicator of clinical worsening in patients (11).

Although CRP and albumin alone are considered prognostic markers in various clinical settings, their combination provides more information about both the inflammatory and metabolic status of the patient (12). In recent studies, some studies have emphasized that the CRP/albumin ratio is related to the patient with coronary artery sclerosis and also the severity of the disease (13, 14). In other studies, it is thought that a high CRP/albumin ratio may be a marker of atherosclerosis in patients with atherothrombotic stroke compared to other types of stroke (15).

In this study, we evaluated the CRP/Albumin ratio from the first blood samples taken in patients who were admitted to the emergency department with suspicion of cerebrovascular accident or who were diagnosed with diffusion MRI or computed tomography by the physician working in the emergency department with the suspicion of cerebrovascular accident. In this study, we found that the CRP/albumin ratio at the time of admission was associated with acute cerebrovascular accident. Additionally, serum albumin, CRP/Albumin and CRP alone levels were significantly different between survivors and non-survivors in our study. Therefore, CRP, albumin CRP/Albumin levels may be equally helpful in predicting the prognosis of patients diagnosed with acute ischemic disease in the emergency department and making early decisions for their treatment. As a result, we think that early CRP levels and CRP/Albumin ratio may help predict the in-hospital mortality of these patients.

Disclaimer: The opinions expressed in the article belong to the authors. There is no official responsibility of any institution or financial source.

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this manuscript.

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